

**NATIONAL -CULTURAL CHARACTERISTICS OF LEXICAL UNITS
EXPRESSING THE ECONOMICAL CONDITION OF A PERSON'S LIFE
IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES**

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Annotation: The article looks at where the concept of material condition of a person in English and Uzbek languages fits into the system of concepts as well as the methods used today in linguistics to figure out how they are structured, which are based on disagreements over the number and type of lexical components. The structure of the idea is established and examined based on a thorough methodology.

Key words: lexical units, methods, concept, material condition, cultural aspects, linguistics.

Аннотация: В статье рассматривается место понятия материального положения человека в английском и узбекском языках в систему понятий, а также методы, используемые сегодня в языкознании для выяснения того, как они структурированы, в основе которых лежат разногласия по поводу количество и тип лексических компонентов. Структура идеи устанавливается и исследуется на основе тщательной методологии.

Ключевые слова: лексические единицы, приемы, концепт,

материальное состояние, культурологические аспекты, языкознание.

Conceptology, whose primary term is concept, holds a special place among the fields of contemporary linguistics. Midway through the 20th century, S.A. Askoldov put it into use in science. The phrase is a fundamental one in many branches of contemporary linguistics, while being a difficult scientific notion. As a result, the idea is interpreted in psycholinguistics as a mental formation that possesses the characteristics of an established and typical image and serves as a replacement. In addition, particular focus is placed on the concept's subjectively important qualities.

Analysis of the national spirit of peoples as it is represented in world languages, identification of ethnocultural aspects of linguistic expression, and research of linguistic units of national and cultural significance using a linguistic method. They rank among the priorities of human relations. It should be mentioned that the main emphasis is on the psycholinguistic, linguocognitive, linguoculturological, and sociolinguistic nature of language as well as how it functions in the lives of various peoples.

The scientific significance of the research findings is the clarification of conceptual and linguistic concept problems, the potential application of the research findings using the methods chosen for the scientific interpretation of linguistic material to further develop in other languages, linguocultural, and cognitive, and the explanation for these possibilities.

The construction of textbooks and manuals on lexicology, phraseology,

sociolinguistics, translation theory and practice in higher education, comparison of the English and Uzbek languages, and teaching specialized subjects are examples of how the research has practical applications. Courses in linguocultural studies, text analysis, dissertations, master's theses, and the English and Uzbek languages can all help prospective professionals to expand their theoretical and practical knowledge.

Language is a part of human nature and is essential for the growth of a person's cognitive abilities and the establishment of their worldview. Language's social and human nature is that it establishes the parameters for all cultural existence. Since Research should be done in a variety of approaches because the ratio of events in the "ethnos-culture-language" triangle is diverse and distinguished by the interdependence of the relationships expressed. The research should first concentrate on the types and forms of speech actions that are unique to a given civilization, before concentrating on the study of their nature and purposes.

The huge distinction between the English and Uzbek etymological and social highlights of the concepts of the internal world of man within the English and Uzbek languages is reflected within the in the within the family parts. For illustration, let's compare the part of a bride in an Uzbek family and a daughter-in-law or bride in an English family. There are numerous customs and traditions related with the picture of the bride (bride welcome, the bride saw), the family obligations and obligations of the bride have long been recorded in a few expressions with the bride component, as it were one express coherent unit is

found in English meaning nation, not bride: the bride of the ocean – Venice.

The phonetic and social highlights of the concepts of the inward world of man in English and Uzbek too incorporate family relations between family individuals and relatives. For illustration, in Uzbek, there are such expressions as kuda-anda, kudalik, kuda-andachilik, and so on, which have no English analogs. N.N. According to Boldirev, a concept in dialect can be verbalized through person words and expressions, express consistent units, sentences, and entire writings. Depending on the substance and level of deliberation, the researcher recognizes a few components of the concept: a clear enthusiastic picture, creative energy, plot, concept, model, propositional structure, outline, script (script), gestalt, etc.

It ought to be famous that this picture is realized as it were within the setting of Uzbek culture. Let's take a see at the considering state made based on the English diction zoo Daddy (a divorced father who has the proper to meet his children on the ends of the week). Here may be a representation of a father who separated his mother on the ends of the week. She takes her children for strolls within the stop, circus, zoo, and other places. Allegorical reexamining: May and December - ancient spouse and young wife. A clear enthusiastic picture can be named specifically: the child of the father - he is just like the father, he is the father's claim.

The etymological and social highlights of the concepts of the inward world of man in English and Uzbek are the mental solidarity of the picture of the world scene, which incorporates both phonetic and social information, creative energy,

and values. The realization of the substance of this concept is done utilizing dialect. All issues, information, values, and values related to the linguocultural highlights of the concepts of the inward world of man in English and Uzbek are reflected within the dialect units.

Consequently, this concept is based on the lexical, state consistent, and literary levels of the dialect, and can be realized in legends talks, society melodies, sayings, and idioms that reflect the shrewdness of the individuals. Linguocultural highlights of the concepts of the internal world of man in English and Uzbek are caught on as a unit of the substance of collective awareness, which is put away within the national memory of dialect proprietors within the frame of phonetic expression. This concept is closely related to a particular linguistic community and its national, social, social, mental, youth, and lifestyle encounters. It has a few profitable, sincerely assessing, and acquainted characteristics.

The linguocultural highlights of the concepts of the internal world of man in English and Uzbek as a multidimensional linguocultural concept are related to the outside and inner world of man and reflect the ethnic character of the dialects being analyzed. As a result of the ponder, phonetic and additional etymological components affecting the flow of advancement of dialect units speaking to family relations in English and Uzbek were recognized.

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